

Spectrophotometric methods for the determination of indinavir sulfate

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Four simple and sensitive spectrophotometric methods for the determination of indinavir sulfate (INS) in bulk samples and pharmaceutical formulations are described. They are based on the oxidation of INS with excess *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS) and the determination of the unconsumed NBS with *p*-*N*-methylaminophenol sulfate (PMAP or metol) – sulfanilamide (SA) (method A, λ_{\max} 520 nm) or celestine blue (CB) (method B, λ_{\max} 540 nm) or by the formation of a chloroform-soluble coloured ion-association complex between INS and tropaeoline OOO (TPOOO) (method C, λ_{\max} 485 nm) or azocaramine G (ACG) (method D, λ_{\max} 520 nm).

Indinavir sulfate (INS), [(αR , gS , $2S$)- α -benzyl-2-(*tert*-butylcarbamoyl)-*g*-hydroxy-*N*-[1*S*,2*R*]-2-hydroxy-1-indanyl]-4-(3-pyridylmethyl)-1-piperazine valeramide sulfate (1 : 1)¹, is an antiviral drug which inhibits the activity of human immunodeficiency virus (HIV). A few methods appeared in the literature for the determination of INS in bulk samples and pharmaceutical formulations involving HPLC², UV³, MS^{4,5}. There is not even a single report based on visible spectrophotometry. Based on the different chemical reactions (redox and ion-association complex formation) four spectrophotometric methods have been developed for the estimation of INS if present in bulk form and pharmaceutical formulations.

Methods A and B are based on the oxidation of INS with excess NBS^{6,7} to form oxidation products. The methods are based on the estimation of reacted NBS either by colour development with PMAP-SA (method A) or decrease in colour intensity of celestine blue (method B). Methods C and D are based on the formation of an ion-associate complex with acid dyes (with method C and with method D) which is extractable into chloroform layer from aqueous phase.

Results and discussion

The reaction conditions were established by variation of one parameter at a time⁸.

Method A involves two stages – oxidation of INS by excess NBS, and estimation of unreacted NBS with PMAP-

SA reagent. In the first stage the oxidation of INS, the use of 1.5–3.0 ml of NBS and a waiting period of 10–20 min were found necessary. In the second stage 5 ml of acetic acid, 1.0–2.0 ml of PMAP solution and 1.0–2.5 ml SA solution were found optimal. The waiting period should be 1–3 min prior to the addition of PMAP and SA.

Method B involves the oxidation of INS with excess of NBS (first stage) and estimation of the unreacted NBS with CB (second stage). In this method 1.3 ml of 5 *M* HCl, 3.0 ml of NBS and 5.0 ml of CB were found to give maximum decrease in colour intensity for reproducible result. Time span of 10 min and 5 min were required in the first and second stage, respectively.

In methods C and D, the INS was allowed to react with the dyes (TPOOO) for the method C, ACG for the method D in the presence of 0.05–1.5 *M* HCl (method C) or glycine buffer of pH 1.2–1.8 in aqueous phase. A 6.0 ml of 0.1 *M* HCl (for method C) or 6.0 ml of buffer solution of pH 1.5 (for method D) rendered maximum absorbance with 2.0 ml of dye. A ratio of 3 : 2 aqueous-to-chloroform ratio with a shaking period of 2 min was found to be optimum for efficient extraction of coloured species into the organic layer.

Interference studies :

The commonly used ingredients and additives in the preparation of formulations such as talc (upto 200-fold excess, w/v), starch (150-fold), boric acid (150-fold), stearic acid (70-fold), magnesium stearate (10-fold), kaolin (30-

fold), sodium lauryl sulfate (10-fold) and gelatin (10-fold) did not interfere with the assay of INS by the proposed methods. However, a preliminary clean up procedure with chloroform was necessary to avoid interference due to the presence of reducing sugars like lactose, if present, prior to the estimation of INS in formulations for methods A and B. Summary of the results are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Optical characteristics, precision and accuracy of the proposed methods of indinavir sulfate

Parameter	Method			
	A	B	C	D
Beer's law limits ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$), c	3–40	0.6–6	1.2–15	1.3–15
Molar absorptivity ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1} \text{cm}^{-1}$)	1.324×10^4	5.624×10^4	2.933×10^4	2.745×10^4
Sandell's sensitivity ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}/0.001 \text{ abs. unit}$)	5.4×10^{-2}	1.26×10^{-2}	2.43×10^{-2}	2.59×10^{-2}
Regression	equation ^a :			
Slope (b)	1.86×10^{-2}	7.8×10^{-2}	4.17×10^{-2}	3.85×10^{-2}
Intercept (a)	2×10^{-4}	1.38×10^{-3}	-2.9×10^{-3}	1.01×10^{-3}
Correlation coefficient (r)	0.9999	0.9999	0.9998	0.9998
Relative standard deviation (%) ^b	0.374	0.591	0.624	0.484
% Range of error (95% confidence limits)	0.39	0.62	0.65	0.51

^a $Y = a + bc$, where c is the concentration of analyte ($\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$) and Y the absorbance unit.

^bCalculated from six determinations.

Commercial formulations (capsules) containing INS were successfully analyzed by the proposed methods. The recovery was 98.7–100.9%. The proposed methods are simple, rapid, sensitive and accurate.

Experimental

A Systronics 106 and Milton Roy spectronic 1201 UV-visible spectrophotometers with 1 cm matched quartz cells were used. An Elico LI-120 pH meter was used.

All reagents were of A.R. grade and all solutions were prepared in triple-distilled water. Freshly prepared solutions were always used.

Aqueous solutions of NBS (Loba; $4.94 \times 10^{-3} M$), metol (Loba; $8.71 \times 10^{-3} M$), SA (IDPL labs; $1.16 \times 10^{-2} M$, initially dissolved in minimum quantity of dil. HCl) and acetic acid (Ranbaxy; $3.75 \times 10^{-1} M$) were prepared for method A. Aqueous solution of NBS ($5.618 \times 10^{-4} M$), CB (Chroma; $5.49 \times 10^{-4} M$) and HCl (B.D.H.; $5 M$) were

prepared for method B. Aqueous solutions of TPOOO (Fluka; $5.7 \times 10^{-3} M$) and HCl (Qualigens; $1 \times 10^{-1} M$) were prepared for method C. Glycine buffer (pH 1.5) and an aqueous solution of ACG (Gurr; $8.75 \times 10^{-4} M$) were prepared for method D.

A 1 mg/ml stock solution of indinavir sulfate (obtained as a gift sample from Cipla, Mumbai) was prepared in distilled water. Working standard solutions of INS (200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for method A, 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for methods B, 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for method C, and 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for method D) were obtained by diluting the stock solution with distilled water.

Procedure :

Method A : Into a series of 25 ml volumetric flasks containing aliquots (1.0–5.0 ml) of INS solution (200 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), NBS (2.5 ml) and acetic acid (5.0 ml) solutions were added successively and the volume was made to 10 ml with distilled water and set aside for 25 min at room temperature. Then metol (1.5 ml) and SA (1.5 ml) solutions were added at 1 min interval and the volume made to 25 ml with distilled water. The absorbance of the solutions were measured against distilled water at 520 nm after 10 min. The colour remained stable for 30 min. A blank experiment was also carried and the decrease in the absorbance corresponding to INS was obtained by subtracting the absorbance of the drug solution from that of the blank. The amount of drug was calculated from the Beer's law plot.

Method B : To each 25 ml graduated tubes containing standard drug solution (0.25–1.5 ml, 100 $\mu\text{g/ml}$), 5.0 M HCl (1.3 ml) and NBS (3.0 ml) were added and the solution in each tube was diluted to 20 ml with distilled water. After 10 min, CB solution (5 ml) was added, mixed thoroughly and the absorbance was measured after 5 min at 540 nm against distilled water. A blank without the drug and dye (devoid of drug and oxidant) was prepared in similar manner and its absorbance was measured against distilled water. The decrease in absorbance corresponding to consumed oxidant, which reflects the drug concentration, was obtained by subtracting the decrease in absorbance of the test solution (dye-test) from that of the blank solution (dye-blank). Calibration graph was prepared by plotting the decrease in the absorbance of dye against the amount of drug. The amounts of INS was calculated from its calibration curve.

Methods C and D : Aliquots of standard drug solution of INS (1.0–5.0 ml, 30 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for method C; 0.5–3.0 ml, 50 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ for method D) were transferred into a series of 125 ml separating funnels. Then 0.1 M HCl (6.0 ml) and TPOOO solution (2.0 ml) (for method C) or 6.0 ml of buffer solution (pH 1.5; 6.0 ml) and ACG solution (2.0 ml) (method D)

were added into the funnels. The total aqueous layer in each funnel was brought to 15 ml with distilled water. A 10 ml portion of chloroform was added to each funnel and contents were shaken for 2 min. The absorbance of the separated chloroform layer was measured after 5 min at 485 nm (for method C) or 520 nm (for method D) against the reagent blank. The amount of INS was calculated from the calibration graph taking the absorbance values into consideration.

Conclusion : The sensitivity (ϵ_{\max}) and selectivity (λ_{\max}) order of the procedures are $B > C > D > A$ and $B > A = D > C$, respectively. The proposed methods are sensitive with reasonable precision and accuracy. Methods B and C are preferable for their better sensitivity compared to other methods.

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